

Conference Abstract

Catching shadows: Development and validation of three primer pairs for eDNA detection of *Umbra krameri*

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Abstract

Environmental DNA (eDNA) is a sensitive, non-invasive approach for surveying rare freshwater fishes, and is particularly effective for species whose low densities and behavioural traits limit conventional detection (e.g., electrofishing). To enable sensitive and reliable detection of the European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) from molecular traces, we developed and compared three species-specific primer sets (Suppl. material 1). First, we assembled the complete mitochondrial genome of *U. krameri* from PacBio HiFi reads to identify suitable regions for primer development. We then designed primer pairs to amplify short fragments targeting three mtDNA loci:

1. a 129-base-pair (bp) fragment of cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI);
2. a 178-bp fragment of NADH dehydrogenase subunit 2 (ND2); and
3. a 217-bp fragment of NADH dehydrogenase subunit 1 (ND1).

The COI and ND2 assays combined primers with FAM-labelled hydrolysis probes, whereas the ND1 assay consisted of primers only (no probe). The specificity was first assessed *in silico* using Primer-BLAST and then tested empirically on tissue derived DNA extracts from 25 fish species occurring in Austrian waters, as well as on 15 eDNA samples from an old Danubian sidearm system (Fadenbach). This system is home to one of the last self-sustaining populations of *U. krameri* within Austrian borders. Potential

method-specific biases were assessed by comparing eDNA detection results with catch data from fish traps collected during the same sampling campaign. This workflow enabled the identification of the most sensitive primer pair, which should be considered for routine monitoring and future conservation assessments.

Presenting author

Hans Rund

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Presentation Rund H. [doi](#)

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